

DIGITAL BANKING MANIFESTO 2.0

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Annotation: This article discusses the future of the banking industry. We are entering a new era of innovation that is reshaping consumers' relationships with their banks. To understand how banking is evolving in the digital age, we need to understand its basic terms and work to prevent potential problems. Opinions of research scientists on the creation of new systems in the banking sector were discussed. Reliable information about the field is enriched.

Keywords: Digital Banking Manifesto, payment systems, Bank loans, banking institutions.

We wrote the original version of the Digital Banking Manifesto in 2016, when the entire economy, including the banking system, recovered from the devastating experiences of the global financial crisis (GFC). We are updating the manifesto in the context of an even greater economic crisis caused by the COVID-19 virus. The GFC was a futile opportunity to restructure the global financial ecosystem. If history has taught us something, the current crisis falls into the same category. Already during the COVID-19 crisis, the introduction of digital banking technology around the world is gaining momentum.

However, reform is urgently needed. Over the last decade, very large and unsuccessful banks have grown rather than smaller, significantly increasing their share in the banking business. For example, J.P. Morgan has nearly twice as many assets in late 2006 as it did before the crisis began; During the same period, the assets

of China's four systemically important banks more than tripled. Although capitalization is better, banking institutions have become so complex that it is difficult to confidently determine their sustainability and creditworthiness. Their balances are not transparent and have risks of complexity that are not well understood by regulators, depositors, investors or even internal management. This complexity can be high and too great to manage.

In addition, large-scale lending does not rely on banks in times of need (as it is now); Instead, central banks are changing their usual lenders — the last resort method — and becoming the last resort buyer instead.

The general public's dissatisfaction with the status quo manifests itself in many ways - in politics, in public discourse, and most directly in the incredible rise and near fall of bitcoin and other cryptocurrencies. However, not all is lost. The introduction of new technologies poses competitive threats to existing players and reshapes the entire financial ecosystem. We anticipate the most intense competition in the following areas: fractional reserve banks to narrow banks, physical cash to digital cash, cryptocurrencies backed by assets against fiat currencies, centralized payment systems and distributed payment systems, and centralized against identification.

We are entering a new era of innovation that is reshaping consumers' relationships with their banks. To understand how banking is evolving in the digital age, we need to understand its basic terms. While smart people may disagree about nuances, the art of banking is to masterfully handle a double-sided general ledger. At the micro level, banks can be seen as dividend-generating machines that seek deposits and provide loans. At the macro level, they are the creators of loan money.

The main factors in the quality and reliability of banks are the amount of capital and the level of liquidity they hold (mainly central bank money and government paper). In general, the bank wants to maintain the correct level of both - if it is too low, it becomes brittle; if it is too much, it becomes useless and therefore

cannot fulfill its purpose of paying dividends. Some of the loans provided by the bank will be repaid as expected, and some will not be repaid. In general, when loans are repaid, bank capital increases; and when they default, bank capital decreases.

If a bank's capital is less than a certain portion of its risky assets, the bank defaults. This setting is the basis of the fractional reserve bank. However, in principle, a bank can be built only in excess of its deposit base with low-risk securities for sale and assets of the central bank consisting of cash. In the absence of operational failures, such a bank cannot withstand default and is more resilient than its smaller reserve brethren.

We know that banking originated in the Upper Middle Ages and flourished in the Renaissance and early modern times, mainly in the form of fractional reserve banking firms that could collapse naturally. From time to time, for example, in Venice and Amsterdam, legislative attempts have been made to shift banking from a fractional reserve to a narrow one. Over time, banks have become much narrower than before or now. In the nineteenth century, British and American commercial banks followed the doctrine of real bills of exchange for their own benefit (where they issued only a fully backed currency with fixed assets) and in line with this approach, mainly short-term loans.

Bank loans were financed mainly by short-term working capital and trade loans, with maturities of two to three months, and secured by the borrower's wealth or transit goods. After the establishment of the Federal Reserve Bank in 1913, commercial banks moved away from the actual promissory note doctrine. They began lending for much longer periods and set up revolving credit lines for some borrowers, thereby sacrificing prudence and increasing their ability to change their maturity. The Great Depression of 1929 showed that banks could not successfully fulfill their obligations, which promoted the idea of a narrow bank.

The practical conversion of fractional reserve banks into narrow banks did not go unnoticed in the 1940s, due to the great political pressure of fractional reserve

banks on the need to increase inflation to eliminate war debts. However, the idea remained close to the surface. It gained great popularity during and after the fund and credit crises of the 1980s and 1990s, and it is not surprising that it became more prevalent during and after the GFC. We show below that technological developments are making the creation of narrow banks an attractive and much-needed opportunity.

Good bankers are distinguished from bad bankers by their ability to attract large sums of money from reliable borrowers, so the default rate remains close to expected values. (Some defaults are inevitable and are taken into account by charging interest.) At the same time, good bankers need to attract long-term depositors and serve them well so that depositors do not return their deposits all at once. If the latter happened, the bank could run out of its liquid reserves and default in another way. In fact, if its less liquid assets are healthy, the central bank, known as the ultimate lender for some reason, can come to the rescue and provide additional liquidity. As can be seen from the above description, banking activities are mainly technological and mathematical. It is therefore very suitable for digitization.

Nevertheless, the prevalence of old systems and legacy cultures prevent banks from embracing innovation as much as they would if they were to survive and thrive in the twenty-first century digital economy. It is not difficult to understand the main reasons for the failure of banking - traditional banks are far behind the latest technological advances; He also has poor management of the risks in his books. While many industries, including retail, travel, communications, and the media, have undergone revolutionary changes in their business models over the past thirty years, banking has regained its glory in the past. Living in its glory, ignoring the winds of change, remained static at its core. Existing banks suffer from many shortcomings because the competition between them is relatively weak.

In addition, their customers are usually not satisfied with the level of customer service. In addition, customers are at risk of losing their deposits (above and below

the normative guaranteed minimum) so that they do not pay their debts to the bank. In recent years, zero or negative deposit rates, which are common in most developed countries, make keeping money in a bank both risky and unprofitable. However, there are currently no viable alternatives for customers. Especially in developing countries, there is a full layer of population and small and medium enterprises (SMEs) that have little or no bank, because traditional banking methods are flexible enough to solve the problem of "knowing your customer" (KYC) it's not a problem for them or an assessment of their creditworthiness.

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